

E3.1 Intermediate prototype of data lifecycle management for adaptive edge intelligence

v1.0

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TO	Herramienta
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1 Introduction

This document outlines the architecture and operational components of an intermediate Proof of Concept (PoC) designed to address the complexities of data lifecycle management in the context of adaptive edge intelligence.

The architecture aims to optimize communication overhead and enhance the efficiency of handling massive and heterogeneous data streams, thereby supporting advanced processes such as transfer learning and real-time, data-driven decision-making.

2 Proposed Architecture for the PoC

2.1 Applications

This PoC includes a set of dummy applications designed to demonstrate a basic scenario. Specifically, it generates four test signals for illustrative purposes. For the sake of simplicity, this guide focuses exclusively on the **producer.ramp** signal (further details provided below).

2.2 Metrics Collection

We employ the OpenTelemetry (OTel) Collector to gather data from the applications. This example is streamlined to focus solely on the applications themselves. However, in a production environment, it's crucial to also consider infrastructure metrics collection.

2.3 Metrics Processing and Storage

The OTel Collector is responsible for processing and forwarding telemetry data to Jaeger, Prometheus, and InfluxDB. This setup ensures that all collected metrics are efficiently processed and stored for further analysis.

2.4. Analysis and Observability

For comprehensive system observability, this PoC integrates Jaeger for trace analysis, alongside Prometheus and InfluxDB for monitoring metrics and managing alerts. This combination offers a complete view of the system's performance and health.

2.5. Data Lifecycle Management

Apache Airflow enhances data lifecycle management by automating the Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) processes. Airflow's scheduling, coordination, and monitoring capabilities make it an ideal tool for managing complex workflows, particularly those involving essential ETL tasks in data management.

2.6. Data Feature Management

Lastly, Feast is utilized for managing data features, thereby streamlining the training and inference processes for machine learning models at the network edge. Feast simplifies the handling of feature data, making it easier to implement and scale ML models.

2 Architecture Diagram

Figure 1 Architecture Diagram

Component	Purpose	Justification
OTel Collector	To collect, process, and export telemetry (metrics, traces, and logs) from services.	Crucial for aggregating telemetry data in a distributed environment, enabling efficient management of communication overhead and facilitating the analysis of massive and heterogeneous data.
Jaeger (Trace Tracking)	To provide trace tracking to understand the flow of requests through the services of producer, sync, fusion, encoder, decoder, and client.	Essential for data visibility in a distributed environment, allowing the identification of bottlenecks, dependencies between services, and optimizing data flow.

Prometheus (Observability Backend)	To collect and store metrics from services, offering a platform for real-time monitoring and alerts.	Supports data visibility and metric management, crucial for monitoring system performance and health, enabling proactive and reactive adjustments in the infrastructure.
Telegraf	To act as a data collection agent that can process and send metrics and event data to InfluxDB.	Its flexibility and ability to integrate with a variety of data sources make it ideal for collecting data from edge services, contributing to the efficient management of massive data.
InfluxDB	To serve as a time-series database for storing metrics and events collected by Telegraf and other agents.	Optimized for the storage and querying of time-series data, facilitates the analysis of trends and patterns in data, essential for data-driven decision-making and data lifecycle management.
Feast (Feature Store)	To manage the storage, access, and serving of data features for ML model training and inference.	Key for the reuse of data features and ensuring consistency and quality in model training, supporting transfer learning and efficiency in data lifecycle management.
Apache Airflow	To orchestrate and automate complex workflows and scheduled tasks in data processing and ML operations.	Facilitates the coordination of task dependencies and the automation of ETL and ML workflows, improving reproducibility, efficiency, and scalability in data lifecycle management and ML operations.

Table 1 Components

3 Getting starter

IMPORTANT!

Feast does not offer support for Windows OS. This limitation is crucial for users planning to deploy or develop with Feast on their local machines or servers.

Recommendation for PoC Installation

For a successful Proof of Concept (PoC) installation of Feast, it is highly recommended to use a Linux-based operating system. Linux offers full compatibility and provides the necessary environment for all Feast functionalities to be explored and utilized effectively.

3.1 Installation guideline (part I)

In this first part is addressed the installation and set-up of Apps, telemetry system and Feast.

Figure 2 Architecture Diagram, Part I

3.1.1 Clone repository

<https://gitlab.i2cat.net/rdprojects/6genablers/6genablers-ai/optare/optare-6g-enablers-lifecycle-management>

3.1.2 Install node and python dependencies.

```
cd ./src/node
npm install
```

```
cd ./src/feast
virtualenv .venv
source .venv/bin/activate
pip3 install -r requirements.txt
```

3.1.3 Run docker-compose.

IMPORTANT!

To prevent issues is commended reset dockers.

```
docker rm -f $(docker ps -aq)
docker volume rm $(docker volume ls -q)
docker rmi -f $(docker images -q)
docker network rm $(docker network ls -q)
docker-compose up
```

you must see following images running:

- lifecycle-management_redis_online2_1
- lifecycle-management_postgres_offline2_1
- lifecycle-management_collector_1
- lifecycle-management_telegraf_1
- lifecycle-management_prometheus_1
- lifecycle-management_jaeger_1
- lifecycle-management_producer_1
- lifecycle-management_sync_1
- lifecycle-management_influx_DB2_1

3.2 Test description

3.2.1 Producer-service

As discussed previously, this service generates a ramp signal. This signal is collected through a customized measurement (gauge) and sent to the OpenTelemetry Collector. It is mandatory for the apps to be equipped with the OpenTelemetry SDK client. The process of adding OpenTelemetry to a Node.js application is illustrated in **src/node/producer-service.ts**.

Figure 3 Producer service.

Custom metric code:

```
const producerRamp = meter.createObservableGauge('producer.ramp', {
  description: 'A signal that increments every second up to 60.'
});
....

// Increments the value of rampValue every second and resets it to 0 when it reaches 60
setInterval(() => {
  const now = Date.now();
  const date = new Date(now);
  date.setHours(date.getHours() + 2);
  const localString = date.toString();
  console.log(`producer.ramp: ${rampValue} at ${localString}`); ....
```

3.2.2 OTel Collector

The OpenTelemetry (OTel) Collector gathers data from the applications and forwards it to the observability backend. You can find the setup in **lifecycle-management/docker-compose/collector/collector.yml**.

Figure 4 OTEL Collector

3.2.3 Observability backends

The metrics and traces will save into Prometheus, InfluxDB and Jaeger.

Jaeger

<http://localhost:16686>

Figure 5 Jaeger UI

Jaeger is a distributed tracing platform released as open source by Uber Technologies. With Jaeger you can:

- Monitor and troubleshoot distributed workflows.
- Identify performance bottlenecks.
- Track down root causes.
- Analyze service dependencies.

Prometheus

<http://localhost:9090>

OpenTelemetry adds a prefix; you should see the `otel_producer_ramp` signal. In the picture, you can observe a ramp signal that increments every 60 seconds. You can find the setup in [lifecycle-management/docker-compose/prometheus/prometheus.yml](#).

```
global:
  scrape_interval: 1m # Default is every 1 minute.

scrape_configs:
  - job_name: 'opentelemetry'
    # metrics_path defaults to '/metrics'
    # scheme defaults to 'http'.
    static_configs:
      - targets: ['collector:8889']
```


Figure 6 Prometheus UI

InfluxDB2

<http://localhost:8086>

- username: admin
- password: admin1234

Figure 7 InfluxDB2 UI

As shown in the previous image, we observe that the same signal is displayed in the Prometheus user interface, in this case, in table format. Pay attention to the applied filter: test->otel_producer_ramp->gauge.

3.3 Feast (Feature Store)

Feast (Feature Store) is a customizable operational data system that re-uses existing infrastructure to manage and serve machine learning features to real-time models.

For simplicity, this example illustrates the ETL process through a Jupyter notebook.

Figure 8 Manual ETL

3.3.1 Execute notebook.

The following notebook: `src/feast/notebook/etl_otel_producer_ramp.ipynb` and verify that the PostgreSQL database has been synchronized with InfluxDB2.

Install jupyterlab if you don't already have it installed.

```
pip install jupyterlab
jupyter lab
```


Figure 9 DBeaver UI

Figure 10 Architecture Diagram, Part II

3.4.1 Run docker-compose.

IMPORTANT!

Run the following command if the dags, logs, plugins, and config folders are not present:

```
mkdir -p ./dags ./logs ./plugins ./config
```

create the airflow-integration network using the following command:

```
docker network create airflow-integration
```

run docker-compose

```
docker compose -f docker-compose-airflow.yml up
```

you must see following images running:

- lifecycle-management-airflow-triggerer-1
- lifecycle-management-airflow-webserver-1
- lifecycle-management-airflow-worker-1
- lifecycle-management-airflow-scheduler-1
- lifecycle-management-airflow-init-1
- lifecycle-management-postgres-1

- lifecycle-management-redis-1

<http://localhost:8080>

username: airflow

password: airflow

you can find DAG sync_influsdb_to_postgres in **dags\dag_etl_otel_producer_ramp.p**

Figure 11 Apache Airflow UI